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SACT: AN ANONYMOUS COMMUNICATION TECHNIQUE

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Abstract:

Objective- The aim of this paper is to realize a secure and anonymous communication technique which provides end-to-end encryption and anonymity simultaneously.

Design/Methodology/Approach- End-to-end encryption and anonymity are considered as important features in privacy preserving communications. A simple combination of Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) and current anonymous communication protocols cannot be used to realize secure and anonymous communication. The anonymity is contradicted by the current PKI because the user is identified by the user's public key certificate. Moreover, there should be certain authentication mechanisms in communication channels because such channels could incubate criminal communication. To deal with this issue, a secure and anonymous communication protocol which employs Identity-Based Encryption (IBE) and group signature is proposed in this paper.

Findings- IBE is used for encrypting packets without sacrificing anonymity and Group Signature scheme is used for anonymous user authentication.

Limitations- In Group Signature scheme, the Group Manager must be a trusted entity as he is capable of breaking the anonymity.

Practical Implications- Proxy entities are used for communication in the protocol which will conceal the user IP address from the Service Providers (SPs), thereby providing anonymity. The system ensures user privacy and provides better security.

Originality- This paper contains works related to anonymous communication as literature survey.

Keywords- Anonymous Authentication, Anonymous Communication, Identity-Based Encryption, Group Signature, Secure Channel

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

Anonymous communication is an important measure to protect the privacy of users, and for protecting computer systems against traffic analysis. Anonymity systems aims to build an infrastructure that runs on top of existing Internet protocols which can allow people to communicate with each other without necessarily revealing their personal network identifiers. The idea behind anonymous system is to provide unlinkability between communicating parties which is achieved by relaying traffic through a number of intermediate nodes. If the messages are delayed and buffered at the intermediate nodes then they can provide stronger anonymity.

Anonymity is an important aspect of privacy, and systems that provide user anonymity are a topic of keen interest currently. Cryptography is used as the building block of constructing such systems; further improvements are needed before they can be used for actual services. An approach to solve anonymous authentication problems is to combine both cryptography primitives and anonymous communication protocols. The current Public Key Infrastructure contradicts anonymity. Therefore it is highly desirable to construct a secure and anonymous communication protocol that achieves end-to-end encryption and anonymity simultaneously. The protocol along with IBE and group signature can allow secure anonymous authentication.

Several cryptographic primitives which can provide anonymity have been proposed. Among this is group signature, which allows signers to anonymously prove the validity of signatures. The Group Manager (GM) has a pair of a group public key, gpk , and a master secret key, msk , and he issues a secret signing key, ski , to a user U_i for computing a group signature, σ , using ski . User-dependent value is not required in the verification phase as the verifier verifies σ using the corresponding gpk only. But, such approaches alone cannot guarantee anonymity. If a signer computes a group signature and sends it to a verifier, then the signature's validity can be anonymously verified by the verifier. But, there is a question of how the group signature can be sent anonymously to the verifier. Usually, a packet consists of a source IP address which reveals the identity of the sender, thus the user anonymity is already infringed.

User IP address is visible in the IP packets sent by the user, and it cannot be simply forged or erased for allowing bi-directional communication. An approach to solve this problem is

to use intermediate agents that can send packets on behalf of the actual user. Several such protocols, like Tor, have already been proposed. However, another issue which arises is assuring the user legitimacy. There is a need to differentiate between legitimate and illegitimate users in order to prevent unauthorized access to a particular channel. One might think that only end-to-end authentication is required, but it is hard to authenticate users without identifying them. For instance, a server needs to send a response code to a user for authentication and the user needs to return a user ID and password. That is, the server has to identify the user. It seems difficult to send a particular message from the server to a user because the corresponding source IP address is normally required. Authentication by using an intermediate agent can be a solution to these problems. The agent can authenticate the user and can hide the user's source IP address from the server. But, there is still a need to know how the server can authenticate the end users directly.

An effective approach to solve anonymous authentication problems is to combine anonymous communication protocols and cryptographic primitives. If a user computes an anonymously-authenticated token, and send it to a server through an anonymous channel. Then, the server can authenticate the user directly without compromising anonymity. However, another problem arises here is how to establish a secure channel. If the server utilizes a user public key in a Public Key Infrastructure, it can identify the user because the certificate contains information of the key holder. Even if symmetric key encryption is used the same problem occurs. Assume that the server attempts to exchange a secret key with an end user. But as the server does not know the actual end user, it does not know the user public key for executing a key exchange protocol. Therefore, though both anonymity and end-to-end encryption are recognized as essential features in privacy preserving communication, the current Public Key Infrastructure contradicts anonymity, so it is highly desirable to construct a secure and anonymous communication protocol which achieves both these properties simultaneously.

II. RELATED WORKS

2.1 ANON-PASS: PRACTICAL ANONYMOUS SUBSCRIPTIONS

Anon-Pass is a protocol and system for anonymous subscription services that allow users to anonymously authenticate while preventing mass sharing of credentials. Service providers

cannot correlate users' actions, yet service providers are guaranteed that each account is in use at most once at a given time. Anon-Pass focuses on practical anonymity, for example, in multi-media services, making all accesses to different items (e.g. articles, songs) appear to be from different users, but not decorrelating access to different parts of the same item. This level of practical anonymity allows Anon-Pass to provide users with flexible service at low cost to the provider. But Anon-pass does not consider end-to-end secure (encrypted) communication.

2.2 PLUG-AND-PLAY IP SECURITY: ANONYMITY INFRASTRUCTURE INSTEAD OF PKI

Plug-and-Play IP Security (PnP-IPsec) is a protocol that establishes an IPsec tunnel between two network gateways without coordinated administration and without relying on a Public Key Infrastructure. The protocol's goal is that if there are two communicating hosts, Alice and Bob, behind two PnP-IPsec gateways, then the gateways will automatically establish an IPsec tunnel to secure all communication between their networks. PnP-IPsec builds on Self-validated Public Data Distribution (SvPDD); namely, each gateway uses SvPDD to retrieve and validate the IPsec configuration from its peer. SvPDD is a protocol that establishes secure connections between re-mote peers/networks, without depending on pre-distributed keys or certification infrastructure. Instead, SvPDD uses available anonymous communication infrastructures such as Tor, which is used to allow detection of MitM attacker interfering with communication. SvPDD may also be used in other scenarios lacking secure public key distribution, such as the initial connection to an SSH server.

They consider two peers, a querier and a responder. The querier specifies a random ephemeral public key that is not certified by the CA, and sends a query that contains this public key to a responder via an anonymous service such as Tor. The responder replies with a message encrypted by the (anonymous) querier ephemeral public key. However, a responder cannot verify whether a public key is a valid key or a random value because this scheme provides no certification of the public key; moreover, the responder cannot even detect whether the public key was replaced by an attacker. Furthermore, no anonymous user authentication is considered in this system.

2.3 DOVETAIL: STRONGER ANONYMITY IN NEXT-GENERATION INTERNET

ROUTING

When we use the Internet, a wide range of identifying information is commonly revealed, but one of the hardest forms of identity to remove is that defined by the network routing protocol (layer 3), since this identity is used to deliver data. In today's Internet, IP is the primary layer 3 protocol and IP addresses are in every data packet. Recording a user's IP address can allow an adversary to uniquely identify her, link that identity with her online activity, correlate connections to different services, and partially reveal her geographical and network locations. Tor is an anonymity system used to conceal a user's identity, including their IP address. Tor has been adopted by hundreds of thousands of privacy-conscious users worldwide. Several anonymity systems, however, work by creating an overlay network on top of the layer 3 protocol, requiring a sequence of IP transmissions to disguise the original sender. This sequential forwarding and the queuing and processing required in intermediary nodes create substantial delay and overhead.

An alternative formulation given for this problem was rather than attempting to conceal a global layer 3 identifier which adds complexity in application protocols, this system believed that the layer 3 protocol should not reveal a global identity. Instead, it leaves identity management to higher layers in the protocol stack, in only those applications where it provides mutual benefit.

While privacy by itself is unlikely to motivate a change away from IP routing, a range of additional concerns have emerged within the networking field, including scalability, security, mobility, challenged environments, and network management, leading to major research initiatives investigating "clean slate" Internet designs that could be used to build the next-generation Internet (NGI). Dovetail is an NGI routing protocol that prevents association of source and destination by an attacker located at any fixed point within the network. Dovetail provides protection against observation by local eavesdroppers and by an untrusted ISP, which is a critical requirement for many privacy-conscious users.

2.4 UNI-DIRECTIONAL CHOSEN CIPHER TEXT SECURE PROXY RE-ENCRYPTION

In 1998, Blaze, Bleumer, and Strauss (BBS) proposed the notion of “atomic proxy cryptography”, in which a semi-trusted proxy computes a function that converts cipher texts for Alice into cipher texts for Bob without seeing the underlying plaintext. Cipher text is the result of encryption performed on plaintext using an algorithm, called a cipher. The goal of such systems is to securely enable the re-encryption of cipher texts from one key to another, without relying on trusted parties.

Proxy re-encryption allows a proxy to transform a cipher text computed under Alice’s public key into one that can be opened by Bob’s secret key. There are many useful applications of this primitive. For instance, Alice might wish to temporarily forward encrypted email to her colleague Bob, without giving him her secret key. In this case, Alice the delegator could designate a proxy to re-encrypt her incoming mail into a format that Bob the delegate can decrypt using his own secret key. Clearly, Alice could provide her secret key to the proxy but this requires an unrealistic level of trust in the proxy. The primary advantage of these schemes is that they are unidirectional (i.e., Alice can delegate to Bob without Bob having to delegate to her) and do not require delegators to reveal all of their secret key to anyone – or even interact with the delegate – in order to allow a proxy to re-encrypt their cipher texts. In these schemes, only a limited amount of trust is placed in the proxy.

Here users first compute re-encryption keys using their secret key and the SP public key, and the SP computes cipher text only using its public key. Then, the proxy can re-encrypt cipher text. However, the proxy needs to manage all re-encryption keys, and therefore, it is difficult to assume that no private information is infringed even if the proxy is corrupted after communication. Moreover, there is a possibility that other users might decrypt unexpected cipher text because the proxy manages many re-encryption keys (from the SP to each user). Generating re-encryption keys that can be used in an unexpected manner is undesirable, even if the proxy is modeled as an honest-but-curious entity and always follows protocol.

III. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing anonymous communication techniques use a combination of current anonymous communication protocols and Public Key Infrastructure (PKI). PKI systems maintain digital certificates, creating and deleting them as needed. The swapping of information is allowed by the

system securely across a public network through a pair of public and private cryptographic keys, that is used for message decryption and encryption. These keys are obtained and accessed through a Certificate Authority (CA). The digital certificate is provided by Public Key Infrastructure, which is an electronic "credit card" that contains the name of the Certificate Authority, user's name, and the effective and expiration dates and the user's public key. During online transactions, user credentials are established by using digital certificates.

3.1.1 DRAWBACKS

- Anonymity is contradicted by the current PKI because the certificate for a user's public key identifies the user.
- PKI-based authentication threatens user privacy.
- Public-key Cryptography is complex and troublesome because the recipient has to be prepared with both public and private keys.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

This paper proposes a secure and anonymous communication protocol. The proposed protocol uses Identity-Based Encryption (IBE) for encrypting the content without identifying key holders. IBE can set arbitrary values on public keys; thus, allowing a user to select a temporary ID for each session that the server can use as a public key. The group signature is also used by the protocol for anonymous user authentication. Communication in the protocol occurs through proxy entities without revealing user IP addresses to Service Providers (SPs).

Identity-Based Encryption (IBE) is a form of Public-Key Cryptography in which a simple identifier is used by the third-party server, such as an e-mail address, to generate a public key that can be used for electronic messages encryption and decryption. Compared with typical Public-Key Cryptography, the complexity of the encryption process is reduced for both users and administrators. An advantage is that a message recipient doesn't need specialized software or advance preparation to read the communication.

Identity-based systems allow generation of public key by any party from a known identity value such as an ASCII string. A trusted third party, called the Key Generation Centre (KGC), generates the corresponding private keys. To operate, the KGC first publishes a master public key, and the corresponding master private key (referred to as master key) is retained. Given the master public key, a public key corresponding to the identity ID can be computed by any party by combining the master public key with the identity value. In order to obtain a corresponding private key, the party authorized to use the identity ID contacts the KGC, which uses the master private key for generating the private key for identity ID. As a result, the messages may be encrypted by parties (or verify signatures) with no prior distribution of keys between individual participants. In the situations where pre-distribution of authenticated keys is infeasible or difficult due to technical restraints, it is extremely useful. However, the authorized user must obtain the appropriate private key from the KGC, to decrypt or sign messages.

The concept of group signatures, introduced by Chaum and Van Heyst, adopts group-based authentication to achieve privacy of signers against potential verifiers. At a high level, group signatures implement the following idea: All potential signers are considered as members of some group. Each signer can issue a signature on behalf of the whole group. Such group signature is publicly verifiable using the public key of the entire group, which provides anonymity of the actual signer. However, there exists a dedicated, possibly trusted party, which can link the group signature to the identity of the signer. We now provide a more detailed view on the architecture behind group signatures and give a brief comparison to the classical PKI authentication.

The architecture of a group signature scheme consists of the group manager and multiple group members. The group manager, which can either be a single authority or a coalition of several entities, is responsible for the initialization of the group, for the admission and in some schemes also for the revocation of group members. During the initialization process the group manager chooses own secret key and defines public group parameters containing the group public key. Once the group parameters are established the group manager can use own secret key to issue membership certificates to the prospective group members. In some schemes the group manager can further use own secret key to revoke existing group members from the group. Each group member is in possession of a membership certificate issued by the group manager. This

certificate represents the secret signing key of the respective group member. That is, each group member can use it to produce group signatures on arbitrary messages. Any verifier can publicly check the validity of some issued group signature using the group public key. Thus the group signature proves that the signer belongs to the group. The distinguished property of group signatures is that the group manager can open group signatures and identify their signers using the information collected during the admission process.

In comparison to ordinary digital signatures, group signatures have extended security goals. In particular, the unforgeability requirement ensures that only group members are able to issue valid group signatures. In addition, group signatures provide privacy by requiring that no other party, except for the manager of the group, should be able to identify the actual signer. Furthermore, group signatures should remain unlinkable, meaning that no party, except for the group manager, can link two or more signatures produced by the same signer.

3.2.1 FRAMEWORK OF THE PROPOSED PROTOCOL

The framework of the proposed protocol has five roles; User, Proxy, SP, GM, and KGC. A User wants to communicate with an SP without revealing its identity. Here, it is assumed that users will never lie about their IP address. The Proxy assists communication between the User and SP by relaying packets without revealing the User IP address. It is assumed that the SP is honest-but-curious. The SP provides services to the User, but wants to authenticate it. The SP is not interested in the identity of the User but wants to confirm whether the User is legitimate. The GM manages a group key and issuer key, and issues a signing key to the User to be used for generating an anonymously-authenticated token. It is assumed that the GM suitably authenticates the User before issuing the signing key. The KGC generates a decryption key for the User. It is assumed that the KGC suitably authenticates the User before issuing the decryption key. These roles need to collaborate mutually in order to realize the proposed secure anonymous authentication.

Fig.4.1 Framework of the Proposed Protocol

3.2.2 ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

No certificates needed as recipient's public key is derived from his identity.

Identity-Based Encryption (IBE) is used. In this process which can be initiated by the sender, for calculating a public key recipient's unique identifier (such as his e-mail address) is used. To calculate the corresponding private key from the public key a trusted third-party server, called the private-key generator, uses a cryptographic algorithm. This is how the recipients can generate their own private keys directly from the server as needed, and also they don't have to worry about distributing their public keys.

Group-based Authentication ensures user privacy.

The authentication process does not disclose any information that could be used to identify some particular user. Group-based authentication is a suitable approach for achieving user privacy, as all disclosed information can only be linked to some group of users.

Group signature scheme ensures unforgeability, anonymity, traceability & unlinkability.

Only members of the group can create valid group signatures. Given a message and its signature, without the group manager's secret key the identity of the individual signer cannot be determined. Given any valid signature, the group manager user issued the signature. (This and the previous requirement show that only the group manager can break users' anonymity). We

cannot tell if the signatures were from the same signer or not if two messages and their signatures are given.

Provide better security.

No unexpected user (including the proxy) can decrypt cipher texts in our protocol because a unique temporary ID is assigned to each user and each session.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION MODELS

4.1 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

There are five main modules. These modules need to collaborate mutually in order to realize the proposed secure anonymous authentication. The modules are:

- ❖ **User Module**
- ❖ **Service Provider**
- ❖ **Proxy**
- ❖ **Group manager**
- ❖ **Key Generation Centre**

4.1.1 USER MODULE

A user is an entity who wants to communicate with an SP without revealing its identity. Here, it is assumed that users will never lie about their IP address. For implementation, a simple client software is prepared that supports the protocol. The software has a command line interface, through which we can send a request to the designated IP address. After sending the request, this software awaits a response from the SP and displays the response upon receiving it. The user module includes Login, Registration, IP Address Manager and Home.

4.1.2 SERVICE PROVIDER

The SP provides services to the User, but wants to authenticate it. The SP is not interested in the identity of the User but wants to confirm whether the User is legitimate. The Service Provider role is implemented using C language. This software awaits requests from the User.

Upon receiving a request from the User, the software runs decryption and encryption using TempID and anonymous authentication using σ before replying to the User.

4.1.3 PROXY MODULE

The Proxy assists communication between the User and SP by relaying packets without revealing the User IP address. The Proxy role is implemented using Tor software and the Simpleproxy. A Simpleproxy generates a child process upon receiving a packet from the User. The process opens a new connection with the destination, i.e. SP, and forwards the packet to the SP. This process maintains separate sessions with the User and with the SP. In this manner any information lower than the session layer is concealed. The IP address information and the port information are hidden. When the session is closed, the process is also closed. One child process is responsible for only one session. In this protocol a new software, called A-Proxy is prepared which is generated by modifying the Simpleproxy. When the child process is generated, A-Proxy extracts the TempID value from the packet sent from the User and stores it inside its repository along with the source and destination IP address. The stored information is deleted by the process before closing the process when the connection is closed.

4.1.4 GROUP MANAGER

The GM manages a group key and issuer key, and issues a signing key to the User to be used for generating an anonymously-authenticated token. It is assumed that the GM suitably authenticates the User before issuing the signing key. The GM module produces a group key and an issuer key.

4.1.5 KEY GENERATION CENTRE

The KGC generates a decryption key for the User. It is assumed that the KGC suitably authenticates the User before issuing the decryption key. The KGC module produces a public key, and a master secret key.

4.2 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig.4.2.1 Overall Architecture

V. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a framework for the proposed protocol. The proposed protocol along with IBE and group signature allows secure anonymous authentication. The complexity lies in enabling both encryption and authentication techniques to work together without sacrificing anonymity. We can see that the protocol is compatible with and deployable over the Internet.

This work can contribute to the management of anonymous communication systems. Assorted anonymous communication systems like Tor carry the risk of being used by malicious parties, but they can be sanitized by introducing our protocol and running anonymous user authentication. In this way, illegitimate users cannot use these systems whereas legitimate users

can still use them without compromising anonymity. Through this work, we wish to facilitate secure, anonymous, and authenticated communication over the Internet.

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